

Artemis meant “The Huntress” from Pre-PIE/PIE *h₂er=”a vehemently strong and violent force that pushes, drives”, cognate with Celtic Artio (a Celtic version of Artemis); and Artemis and Artio are cognate with (but not necessarily deriving from) PIE *h₂ṛtkos “bear”, but *h₂ṛtkos did not mean “Hunter”, but instead derives from ”a vehemently strong and violent force that pushes, drives” because *h₂ṛtkos originally referred to the constellation Ursa Major/the Celestial Chariot, which was imagined to be the driver of the turning of the World-Axis; plus a new etymology of Kottyto/Kotys, and more; and how all these goddesses of the Hunt relate to the Great Bear, Christmas trees, Christmas, the world tree, the North Pole, the Axis Mundi, Rebirth, and Resurrection

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My updated theory regarding the etymology of Ancient Greek Ἄρτεμις and the Ancient Doric Greek variant Ἄρταμις ¹ (and Lydian *Artimus*, whether native to Lydian or not) has some important differences and additions as compared to my previous theory (my previous theory was published January 26^h, 2024; see that draft for more about my previous theory) where I posited that the Art- of Artemis comes from a root that meant “pointed; to prick, to stab, to strike; to cut”², and I had stated in that January 2024 draft that from “to prick” developed the meaning “to prick as in to set something moving, germinating, sprouting” referring to her association with childbirth as well as referring to the Great Bear constellation being viewed as the propeller of the rotation of the axis mundi, of the revolving of the sky (actually the revolving earth, but to ancient peoples it seemed like the sky was revolving) and the changing of the seasons.

1 goddess of the hunt, of childbirth, of the moon; and of the Great Bear constellation; and of quite more as I will detail in this paper.

2 Even before my second draft (published January 26th, 2024), in my first draft from early 2022 I had already posited that the Art- of Artemis came from a root that meant “pointed; to prick, to stab, to strike; to cut”, but in my early 2022 draft I wasn’t sure whether the root was IE or Non-IE, from a Non-IE Pre-Greek language.

Here are the main important differences between my updated July 2024 theory (which I first publicized in comments of mine posted on Academia.edu on July 7th, 2024 and July 8th, 2024³) and my January 2024 theory:

My updated theory posits that the root of the Art- of Artemis/Artamis/Artimus (and likely also the root of the probable Thracian theonym Ara inscribed on a gold ring found near Ezerovo in 1912; and probably also the root of Artio, a Celtic bear-associated goddess) is a Pre-Proto-Indo-European/Proto-Indo-European root **h₂er* which meant "a very strong force that pushes, drives", which led to "Huntress" (as we shall see in some upcoming paragraphs in this edition),

3 Here is one of the comments I had posted on July 8th:

"I remembered some things I was talking about in my paper on Artemis, Artio and **h₂rtk'o-*, and in some other recent papers of mine: the constellation Ursa Major was identified by many ancient peoples as the impeller of the axis of the revolving night sky, the night sky with its revolving constellations. Because of the location of Ursa Major in relation to the sky's north pole.

The shoulder came first because the shoulder was viewed as the location of the motive impetus that moves the arm: as the axle of a wheel was viewed as the mover. So my updated theory (nearly arrived at in my draft) is that PIE **h₂er* comes from "a vehement strong force that impels", shifting to "shoulder"/"axis" and then to "any joint; to join together".

PIE **h₂rtk'o* involves the old root meaning, and referred to the constellation, which was viewed as a bear; **h₂rtk'o* was not their oldest word for "bear"; later this **h₂rtk'o* word was transferred to general bear usage, in many cases displacing older bear words.

PIE **h₂er* was originally semantically parallel to (among other roots such as **h₂ek's*) PIE **weyh₁*, from which comes Latin *Vis* (force, strength, vigor, a vehement rushing force and pretty much a pushing force) and from which comes the source of the word "violent", as one sees in the linguistic references; (this parallels the Tocharian word we discussed earlier) and many words deriving from PIE **weyh₁* have to do with a force that drives something onward, in the case of **weyh₁*, prey that is driven to run away from a pursuer. With the Pre-PIE **h₂er*, this lead to the goddess Artemis, Artio etc., whose names therefore didn't mean Bear, but instead meant Huntress, from "one who drives/impels".

And here is another: "The Ursa Major/Great Bear constellation was also viewed—often by the same people—as a wagon/chariot, originally thought of as the chariot that pulls the Sun and/or the Heavens as they turn. So there again, the axle/axis/shoulder/hip, the hip being to the leg what the shoulder is to the arm: the axle/axis at the top of the limb, likened to the axle/axis at the top of the world.

I am committed to this theory which is from my own observations and all-new, but committed to it because I think it will weather all storms, not because I thought of it: and it took a lot of new info and debate for me to finally think of it, and I consider that I observed it, and in that sense it's not from me, it's from the PIE language and I happen to be the one who finally saw it.

Now many dominoes will go into their proper place: Ancient Greek *artos* ("bread") I now think is from PIE **h₂er* from the semantics "prepared; put together", as we see some Germanic words meaning "yeast" deriving from the semantic "prepared, ready" (see Old Norse *gerð*, et al.) but from a different root, not from **h₂er*.

See Tocharian A: *ārwar* "prepared, ready" and Tocharian B: *ārwer* "prepared, ready etc." considered to be from PIE **h₂er*.

Ancient Greek *artamos* ("butcher") I think is very likely from "the one prepares (the meat)", from PIE **h₂er*. I have no one else positing these etymologies for *artos* ("bread") and *artamos* ("butcher"). That's a better etymology for "butcher", and that's another reason I say that the dominoes are going into their correct place now.

I no longer am wondering about the etymology of **h₂rtk'o-*, and now it's time to see how many etymologies can now be solved with the new gains in information."

On July 7th I had posted the earlier version of what I had realized: "when I read Pinault's paper, what I saw is that *rätkware* is likely cognate with **h₂rtk'o*, but it is very unlikely that the meanings "pungent, violent, stinging" come from the meaning "bear"; instead, if they are cognate, the meaning "bear" would come from the

and which also referred to how Artemis was invoked to help bring about a successful childbirth: to drive the baby out, push the baby out.

A root **h₂er* "a very strong and violent force that pushes, drives" I also posit as the source of PIE **h₂f^tkos* "bear", because I posit that in Pre-PIE/PIE times, **h₂f^tkos* referred to the Ursa Major/Great Bear constellation, a constellation which was closely identified/associated with Artemis (and the Bear of the constellation was almost always if not always thought of as a female bear, hence Ursa Major, not Ursus Major) and a constellation which was viewed by many ancient peoples as the Driver of the rotation of the World-Axis/the Axis Mundi (the apparent rotation of the heavens, which is actually the rotation of the earth on its axis and the orbit of the earth around the sun): I will locate my references for this ancient conception soon enough, for now I will point out that the Ursa Major constellation was also often viewed (often by the same people who viewed it as a giant bear) as a Celestial Chariot/Wagon, which pushed/pulled the sun as it rises and sets, and/or pushed/pulled the heavens as they turn; whether driving or pulling, or both, the result is that the Celestial Chariot was conceived (mythologically if not taken as a literal fact) as being responsible for the movement.

The constellation Ursa Major was also identified with the north, and in Ancient Greek ἄρκτος (variant ἄρκος) meant "the North" as well as "bear", hence even today most European languages use the term Arctic/Arctique to describe the far north and the north pole area: Arctic/Arctique of course deriving from Ancient Greek ἄρκτος= "bear" and "the North", and ἄρκτος and its variant ἄρκος derive from PIE **h₂f^tkos*, which I posit meant "bear" and "the constellation Ursa Major" and "the North Pole (believed to extend invisibly from earth to the sky)" in Proto-Indo-European. The meaning shift from the Ursa Major constellation/North Pole/North point of the world-axis to "bear" was facilitated by the fact that the constellation was perceived by many people in different parts of the world as a bear, and facilitated by the fact that bears are large, mighty and often violent creatures who were often preying on humans, creatures of great strength and great speed when they charge, so the creatures fit the root-meaning **h₂er* "vehemently strong; violently forceful" very excellently, and many ancient peoples imagined that the creature-constellation that drives the turning of the sky must be a mighty creature: therefore, the bear was usually chosen to be the creature of the constellation we know as Ursa Major.

This PIE/pre-PIE **h₂er* "a very strong and violent force that pushes, drives" (a root that I'm positing based on the findings published in this paper) lead to the meanings "axis, axle, shoulder, hip", later shifting to "any joint; to join together; to fit together", which is, of course, the PIE **h₂er*; "to join together; to fit together" known from Indo-European handbooks.

meanings "vehemently strong, forceful, pungent, violent", with "pungent" coming from "very strong" and "stinging" coming from "pungent".

And PIE **h₂er* "to join, together, fit together" could come from the Pre-PIE meanings "firm, dense, pressed together" leading to "to join together, to fit together (to make firm, compact, to make it pressed together)", and the Pre-PIE meanings "firm, dense, pressed together" could come from the earlier meanings "strong, forceful" leading to "firm, dense, pressed together", so that **h₂rtk'o* doesn't come from PIE **h₂er*, "to join, to fit together" instead they both (along with the Tocharian B word, making three) derive from a common ancestral **h₂er* "vehemently strong, forceful, etc."

This is now one of my new theories for the etymology of **h₂rtk'o* "bear". Copyright applies. Plagiarists may receive a nighttime visit from a man in a ninja costume. It's quite likely that the bear's mighty strength and speed and size and bulk were what was being referenced, not the paw nor the tearing claws and cutting claws, fangs etc. Which is quite likely and a good origin for a bear word."

Compare how Latin *axilla* (=armpit, little wing) and Latin *āla* (“wing”, “armpit”, “shoulder-blade”; “the hollow where a tree limb joins the tree”) and Proto-Germanic **ahslō* (“shoulder”) derive from PIE **h₂ek_s-* “axle, axis”, which J. Pokorny, J.P. Mallory and D.Q. Adams correctly posit as deriving from an s-stem **h₂eǵ-os ~ *h₂ǵ-es-os* of PIE **h₂eǵ-* “to drive”, a root which in other papers of mine I further posit as deriving from earlier “a vehemently strong force that drives, impels, pushes; force; a power that is violent in its vehemence” (violent in the sense of, for example, the Big Bang or a supernova).

There are no words meaning “wrist” nor “elbow” deriving from **h₂ek_s-* nor from **h₂er-*, and this is because the beginning of the limbs/the tops of the limbs---the beginning/tops of the limbs being the shoulders and hip sockets---were viewed as the location of the impetus of the motive force, and the top of the limbs were evidently likened to the top of the world, the north pole of the world-axis.

My primary evidence that PIE **h₂ǵtkos* (a noun meaning “bear”) and **h₂ǵtko* (an unattested PIE adjective) derive from a **h₂er* which meant “a very strong force that pushes, drives” is the Tocharian B adjective *rätkware*, which meant “pungent, stinging, violent; strong” and perhaps could also mean “severe, excessive”, a word which Georges Pinault posits as being derived from the meanings “bear<the pawed one”>; he believes that “bear” derives from “paw”, with “paw” deriving from PIE **h₂er*, “joint; to join together, to fit together”. However, from a survey of the words deriving from PIE **h₂er*, it is clear (and this is already acknowledged by the authorities) that the meanings “shoulder” and “hip” came before “arm, leg” and “hand, paw”; I have no example where a word descending from PIE **h₂er* means only “hand/paw”: in all the examples that I know of, if a word from that root developed the meaning “hand” (transferred from the meaning “arm”, in turn from “shoulder”), it still also has the meaning “arm”, which is older; and I know of only one example where the meaning “paw” developed, in an Indo-Iranian language called Khotanese where we find *ārra* meaning “arm; hand; paw”, but the word, as we see, does not mean only “paw”. Khotanese *ārra* derives from PIE **h₂er-mó-s ~ *h₂ǵ-mó-*, and all the words meaning “arm, hand” (and at least one word also meaning “paw”) derive from that **h₂er-mó-s ~ *h₂ǵ-mó-*, though we find Latin *artus* which can refer to the limbs, but not only the arm: the legs as well.

Aside from the “-m” suffixed forms (all deriving from **h₂er-mó-s ~ *h₂ǵ-mó-*), only Latin *artus* approaches close enough to entertain Pinault’s theory, and yet Latin *artus* meant “a joint; sinew, strength, power;” and poetically was used to refer to the limbs as well. Despite the paw being such a major part when one thinks of a bear, and despite the argument that the semantic shift from “shoulder” to “arm” to “hand, paw” perhaps could have occurred quickly enough to account for **h₂ǵtkos* “bear” (just maybe it occurred quickly enough, but I don’t think so, because the words deriving from PIE **h₂er* don’t indicate such an early shift, especially not the -t- suffixed words deriving from **h₂er*), I think that **h₂ǵtko(s)* goes back even before the meaning “arm” developed, let alone “hand” and “paw”.

I propose that Tocharian B *rätkware*, which meant “pungent, stinging, violent; strong” (and perhaps could also mean “severe, excessive”) comes from the earlier meanings “vehemently strong (vehemently strong to the point where the idea of violence arises)”, with “vehemently strong” leading to “violent” and “pungent”; and “pungent” leading to “stinging” etc.

See how “pungent taste” is best defined as “having a strong taste that stings the tongue” and “pungent smell/pungent odor” is best defined as “having a strong smell/odor that stings the nose”. And see how “violent” derives from Latin *violentus*, in turn from *violō*, in turn from PIE *wéyh₁/*weyh₁* “to

chase, pursue; to rush forth with a vehement force”, from where Proto-Italic *wīs “strength, force, power” also derives, the source of Latin vīs=“force, power, strength, vigor, faculty, might, potency; violence, assault; energy”.

And I propose that **h₂f^htko(s)* arose from the meaning “a strong, vehement force that drives, pushes, impels”, referring to the Great Bear/Chariot/Wagon constellation which was widely imagined as being the driver of the World-Axis/Axis Mundi; so then the word referred to the constellation first, later shifting to the bear; unless the constellation was referred to by a term deriving from **h₂f^ht-* or **h₂ert-*, and the suffix *-ko(s)* came about to apply the word to the earthly mammal. In either case **h₂f^htko(s)* would not have been their oldest word for “bear”, and **h₂f^htko(s)* would have in some cases displaced older words for bear in their language. In Ancient Greek ἄρκτος (variant ἄρκος) meant ‘bear’ and ‘the North’.

The root-meaning that I propose---“a strong, vehement force that drives, pushes, impels”, --- explains why the word was applied to the shoulder and to the hip before being applied to the arm, leg, hand, paw, feet, etc.; and this explains why the emphasis is on shoulder and hip, not on elbow, knee, wrist, ankle: because the strong, vehement force that drives, pushes, impels was thought of as being at the top of the limb (shoulder and hip), and this idea was taken from the word’s earlier application: the axis/axle located at the celestial North Pole, the top of the world.

If the Tocharian B adjective *rätkwäre* derives from a PIE adjective **h₂f^htko*, an intermediary form would have to be an adjective **h₂retkuro*⁴. The transition from a hypothetical **h₂retkuro-* back to a **h₂f^htko* is speculative however, and raises some problems and questions. Given our current knowledge of Tocharian and PIE, it seems possible that **h₂retkuro* can derive from **h₂f^htko*. But **h₂retkuro* and **h₂f^htko* may instead be parallel adjectives, originally having the same meaning (“vehemently strong, forceful”), which developed from the same root (from the root **h₂er* with the root meanings that I posit above) along different pathways.

Originally, I posit that the **h₂ert-* in the earlier form of Artemis/Artamis/Artimus meant “to drive, impel, push; and all of these actions done with a vehement, rather violent force”, from there developing the meaning “Hunter/Huntress” (compare the Arcadian myths of Arkas, the great hunter, son of Callisto, a huntress-maiden nymph who was part of Artemis’ retinue: Arkas and his mother Callisto were both turned into physical animal bears, at different times, then Callisto was turned into Ursa Major and Arkas into Boötes; Arkas is thought to mean “bear”: while it is cognate with Arkos/Arktos meaning “bear”, I expect that in earlier times, Arkas would have been understood as meaning “Hunter”: later in Part 2, I will detail the Arkas and Callisto myths more) as we see when studying the words that derive from PIE **weyh₁* “to chase, pursue; to rush forth with a vehement force”⁵:

See for example Proto-Balto-Slavic **wī^htei* “to drive away, chase, pursue”; Latin *violō*, “to treat with violence, to maltreat”; Proto-Italic **wīs* “strength, force, power”, from PIE *wéyh₁s* “force, vehemence”, in turn from PIE *wéyh₁/*weyh₁* “to chase, pursue; to rush forth with a vehement force”:

4 The intermediary reconstruction **h₂retkuro* is according to the linguist Georges Pinault. Georges Pinault is the first to publish (and probably the first to think of the idea that) Tocharian B *rätkwäre* is cognate to PIE **h₂f^htko*, and Pinault is the first to reconstruct an intermediary form **h₂retkuro*.

5 Here is a quick reference for the reader, it’s from Wiktionary which occasionally has errors and other times often gives undue weight to one theory over others, but in this case, Wiktionary editors have not steered the words towards my theory, of which they are unaware of: [Reconstruction:Proto-Indo-European/weyh,- - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Reconstruction:Proto-Indo-European/weyh,-)

Proto-Italic *wīs “strength, force, power” is the source of Latin vīs=“force, power, strength, vigor, faculty, might, potency; violence, assault; energy”; and from this same root *weyh₁ derive a number of words that mean “hunter, huntress; to hunt”.

So combining these linguistic indications with the fact that she was a Huntress Goddess number one above all else in Classical times, this is why I posit that Artemis/Artamis/Artimus meant “the Huntress” originally, not “the Bear”, nor “Archer”, nor any other meaning one might imagine; however, the word probably came to overlap with the meaning “bear” even in PIE and Proto-Greek, as indicated especially with the Celtic goddess Artio/Artiu.

I do not know whether the suffix *-kō* was present in the earlier form of the theonym; if it was present, this would have caused an Artemis/Bear identification to come about long ago.

The theonym and the Ursa Major term may have had the suffix *-kō* in common, because both are nouns referring to mythologically living beings (the goddess and the personified constellation, both are living beings in mythology/religion), and both the meaning “Huntress” and the meaning “bear” came (if this theory is correct, and it looks to be) from “the one who forcefully drives/impels/pushes” (and “bear” derives from such a meaning because the name/word for the constellation was transferred to the animal, as described earlier) : but if the suffix was present in the source of Artemis/Artamis, then it seems that the theonyms must be loans into Greek, since we do not find Arktemis/Arkemis/Arktamis/Arkamis; if not loans into Greek, they would have to be loans from a quite divergent variety of “Greek” or para-Greek; but if the suffix was not present in the theonym, then Artemis/Artamis can be native to Greek.

Indications that Artemis/Artamis may derive from *h₂ʹtkō- are found in connection with Artakēnē: in one of his mimes (“mimes” in this case are short humorous dramatic scenes in verse) the Ancient Greek author Herodas/Herondas (probably of 3rd century BC Alexandria), an author of short plays called “mimes” (none of the extant mimes of Herodas have more than 3 characters) Artakēnē is mentioned twice as a daughter of Hecate. And in a Greek inscription from Pulpudeva/Kendreiseia, we find Artakēnē as an epithet of Hēra, and the inscription invokes Hēra Artakēnē to help with childbirth (and most likely to help the mother survive the childbirth as well), and helping facilitate a successful childbirth is one of the most important functions of Artemis and Hēra, indicating that Artakēnē is a Thracian Artemis, since we find so many Thracian items beginning with Artak-, including the name of a Thracian tribe known as the Artakioi/Artakoi, a tribe described as “warlike”, indicating my etymology of *h₂ʹtkō- from “a vehemently strong, violent force”.

To what extent and in what epoch of time---if in any epoch---was Artemis thought to mean “The Bear” in Greek and Proto-Greek? There are hints of such a blending in the Greek material, which I may detail next time. But as I’ve made clear by now, I do not agree with the etymology that says that Artemis/Artamis actually etymologically meant “bear”.

Nor do I agree with any Non-IE origin of Artemis/Artamis/Artimus: Beekes suggests that the theonym Artemis/Artamis/Artimus is of Non-IE, Pre-Greek origin, but it is unbelievable to think that Artemis is not to be identified with the Celtic goddess named Artio (compare the attested Gaulish word *artos* meaning “bear”, from PIE *h₂ʹtkos “bear”), and Artio was depicted along with a bear⁶ in a bronze sculpture from the Muri statuette group in Bern, Switzerland, which shows a large bear facing a

6 Michaël Ripinsky-Naxon, *The Nature of Shamanism: Substance and Function of a Religious Metaphor* (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1993), 32

woman seated in a chair, with a tree behind the bear. The woman seems to hold fruit in her lap, perhaps feeding the bear.

The sculpture has a large rectangular bronze base, which bears the inscription "Deae Artioni / Licinia Sabinilla" ("To the Goddess Artio" or "Artionis", "from Licinia Sabinilla"). If the name Artio is Gaulish but the syntax is Latin, a dative *Artioni* would give an i-stem nominative **Artionis* or an n-stem nominative **Artio*. That would correspond to a Gaulish n-stem nominative **Artiu*. I will discuss the main encoded meanings of the scene that the sculpture presents in Part 2 of this paper.

Suffice it to say that I do not think that the theonym Artio is unrelated to Gaulish *artos* "bear" (but nor do I assume that Artio derives etymologically from the meaning "bear"), and I do not expect that the theonym Artio is unrelated to the theonym Artemis. The Thracian theonym Artakēnē indicates my theory, as does the Arcadian myths of Arkas, the great hunter, son of Callisto; and the myth of Callisto, both of which I will detail later in Part 2.

PIE **h₂rtkós* "bear" and the Tocharian B adjective *rätkware* are more likely to be close cognates than :

PIE **h₂rtkós* "bear" vis-à-vis Sanskrit *rákṣas* ("harm, injury, damage") and Avestan *rašah* (*id.*);

because there is no evidence that there was an **h₂* laryngeal, nor evidence that there was a T in the root of these Sanskrit and Avestan words: for example, the LIV posits a PIE **h₁reks-* "to damage" as the root of Sanskrit *rákṣas* ("harm, injury, damage") and Avestan *rašah* (*id.*): note that the hypothetical reconstruction **h₁reks-* begins with the **h₁* laryngeal (not an **h₂*) and does not contain a T sound; but neither the **h₁* nor the **h₂* have been proven for the root of these Sanskrit and Avestan words, nor can the presence of a T sound nor the lack of a T sound be proven yet.

Specht many decades ago seems to have been the first to propose that **h₂rtkós* "bear" derives from a hypothetical PIE adjective **h₂rtkós* ("destroying") or from from a hypothetical PIE **h₂rétkos* ~ **h₂rétkes* ("destruction"), forms which he reconstructed by comparing **h₂rtkós* "bear" with Sanskrit *rákṣas* ("harm, injury, damage") and Avestan *rašah* ---but I have a better theory for the actual root-meaning and the actual semantic range of the root from which PIE **h₂rtkós* "bear" derives, and so these Sanskrit and Avestan words I'm pretty sure are not the source of PIE **h₂rtkós* "bear" ; the Sanskrit *rákṣas* ("harm, injury, damage") and Avestan *rašah* may be unrelated to PIE **h₂rtkós* "bear", but I find it more likely that these Sanskrit and Avestan words trace back to the same root from which **h₂rtkós* "bear" derives, since the meanings of these Sanskrit and Avestan words seem like they can easily derive from the meaning "to assault", a meaning which easily derives from "vehement force that is often violent" etc.: I don't need to spell out more details about that semantic shift, one can (if they need to) go and read some of the paragraphs above if one needs an explication for that. If these Sanskrit and Avestan words derive from PIE/pre-PIE **h₂er*, "a strong, vehement force that drives, pushes, impels", then the intermediary forms should most likely all begin with **h₂*, but a T sound would not be necessary, since in this scenario they do not derive directly from **h₂rtkós* but instead from the same root from which **h₂rtkós* derives⁷.

7 It doesn't seem morphologically/phonologically possible for Sanskrit *rákṣas* ("harm, injury, damage") to derive directly from Sanskrit *ṛkṣa* ("bear"), and the same goes for the Avestan *rašah* ("harm, injury, damage") and Avestan *arša* ("bear"). Nor is the semantic shift from "bear" to "harm, injury, damage" so likely, given that there were also lions and tigers and wolves familiar to the Indo-Aryans, creatures that are more likely to prey on humans. Though bears were the ones destroying beehives.

Ancient Greek ἐρέχθω (“to rend, break”) cannot be a direct cognate of Sanskrit *rākṣas* (“harm, injury, damage”) and Avestan *rašah* (*id.*) due to the “kh” sound in the Greek word (and the aspirated T may also be a problem), but they may be parallel forms from the same root along different branches, with different suffixes attached, with the root being **h₂er*, “a vehement strong force; a violent force”, with “a violent force” leading to “to rend, break”.

The Sanskrit word *ṛkṣá* meaning “bald, bare” I take to be unrelated to Sanskrit *ṛkṣa* “bear” (which is from PIE **h₂ṛtkos*) and unrelated to PIE **h₂ṛtkos*.

I expect that *ṛkṣá* (“bald, bare”) is a hyper-correction of Sanskrit अच्छ (accha), from Sanskrit अ- (=a-, “not”)+ Sanskrit छ (=cha, “shaded”); the second component being related to Sanskrit छद् (chad, “to cover; to hide”). It would be a hyper-correction because some Sanskrit speakers probably came to think that accha is a Pali “corruption” of an imagined earlier “*ṛkṣá*” (“bald, bare”) form, because they knew that Pali had “corrupted” *ṛkṣa* “bear” to अच्छ (accha) = “bear”. New-born bear cubs (at least of some species) are born without fur, but the furless stage doesn’t last long and mother bears being so protective of the cubs at that age in their dens, more civilized humans (as opposed to Paleolithic humans etc.) rarely saw the cubs furless.

Nor do I think that Sanskrit *ṛkṣá* (“bald, bare”) is from the semantic “shaved/scraped” as I had posted (though I presented it as a theory) in a comment on Academia.edu back when I thought that **h₂ṛtkos* “bear” probably derived from a root meaning “to scratch, cut, tear; stab, prick”, a semantic set which would have been parallel to the semantics of the Albanian word *ther*: which means “to cut, to gut, to prick, to pierce, to slaughter”⁸.

Now it is time to discuss the *-emis /-amis* portion of Artemis/Artamis: I conclude (contrary to Szemerényi, and his theory has not been accepted⁹) that the *-emis/-amis* portion of the

8 See the entry: [ther - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](#); of course I have verified these meanings with authoritative references.

9 In early 2022, some weeks after I already had written out on paper my theory that the Art- of Artemis came from the meanings “pointed; to prick, to stab, to strike; to cut” and some weeks after I had written out my theory that Artemis meant Spearer/Striker/Sagittaria (not to be confused with Sagittarius, because Sagittaria simply means “Arrow woman” in Latin, and does not contain the word “taurus” like Sagittarius does), I found a work from the 1990s by Szemerényi, where he posited that the Arte- in Artemis derives from PIE **h₁ṛstis* (=spear; lance; sword), a PIE root which is based mostly or solely on Indo-Iranian examples (Sanskrit *ṛṣṭi*=“spear, sword, lance”; Old Persian/Late Avestan *aršti-*, “id.”).

He also posited that the “-mis” in Artemis is derived from Pokorny’s alleged PIE root-word **smeit*, --“to throw”, which has words from only two languages, Avestan and Latin, to justify its existence, and the Latin example *mittō* is alternatively derived from PIE **meytH-*, “to exchange” by other sources. If there was a PIE root-word **smeit*, --“to throw”, there is no trace of it in Ancient Greek, and none of the Ancient Greek words and names that end with *-mis* show the slightest indication that any meaning of “to throw” existed for any of the *-mis/ -mition/ -mitios* attestations in Ancient Greek: excluding Artemis/Artamis, the only Ancient Greek forms for which such a meaning can be argued, albeit with no supporting evidence, making Szemerényi’s theory highly unlikely, for two reasons 1) since he’s arguing that not only did *-mis* have that meaning, but that it was a native Greek meaning from PIE **smeit*: not impossible, but quite unlikely that such a form would only survive in one theonym; and 2) we see how such suffixes which do not mean “to throw” commonly bind to the sonic form Art- in Ancient Greek.

So I have no doubt that Szemerényi was wrong about the *-mis* in Artemis meaning “to throw” and deriving from PIE **smeit*: it surely did not mean “to throw” and does not derive from PIE **smeit*. It is simply a suffix as I described above. Furthermore, I’m sure that the Arte- portion does not derive from PIE **h₁ṛstis*, for the reasons

theonyms is only a suffix, a suffix of a type which in Ancient Greek often binded to stems/roots that had the form Art- (stems that had the sonic form Art-, but had different meanings because there were three different root-words which are the sources of the Art- words in Ancient Greek, each particular word deriving from one of the three), a suffix of the type seen in words such as:

ἄρτέμων (=“the foresail of a ship“; in this case the ἄρτ- derives from ἄρτάω, which is from ἀείρω, which is from Proto-Hellenic *aweřřō--,“to lift, raise“, from PIE *h₂wér-ye-ti , which is PIE *h₂wer- “to lift, raise”, with those other morphemes suffixed to it);

ἄρτημα (=“hanging ornament; ear-ring“, also from PIE *h₂wer-);

ἄρτεμής (= “sound; safe and sound“, from ἄρτιος=“complete; perfect; suitable; exactly fitted; full-grown; of sound body and mind; prepared; ready”, from PIE *h₂er- =”to fit; join together”);

ἄρταμέω (=“to cut in pieces; rend asunder“); this word is attested apparently only once, and in an Ancient Greek anthology. I derive it from the noun ἄρταμος, from the sense “butcher”.

ἄρταμος (=“butcher, cook“): I derive this word from the sense “the one who prepares (meat, food)”, hence the word meant “cook” as well as “butcher”. The meaning “the one who prepares (meat, food)”, I derive from “to prepare, make ready, put together”, from PIE *h₂er- =”to fit; join together”. See Tocharian A ārwar meaning “prepared, ready; eager, willing” and Tocharian B ārwer meaning “prepared, ready; eager, willing” , both from Proto-Tocharian *ārwer , from PIE *h₂er- =”to fit together; to join together”.

And we find also a „-um“ form to be included among the suffixes of this type, seen in words such as ἄρτυμα (=“condiment; seasoning“ and „custom, usage“; the ἄρτ- in this word is from ἀρτύω=”to arrange; devise; prepare; make ready; to dress food; to season food”, from PIE *h₂er- “to fit; to join; to put together”).

Part 2

For more support for my theory about *h₂řřtkos being cognate to a word that meant “Hunter/Huntress” from which I posit Artemis derives, see this quote:

“In Greek mythology, Arcas (Ancient Greek: [Ἀρκάς](#): Arkas meant “Bear” in Ancient Greek) was a hunter who became king of Arcadia. He was remembered for having taught people the arts of weaving and baking bread and for spreading agriculture to Arcadia.

Callisto was a nymph in the retinue of the goddess Artemis, or in some sources the daughter of King Lycaon. As she would not be with anyone but Artemis, Zeus cunningly disguised himself as Artemis and raped Callisto. The child resulting from their union was called Arcas.

Hera became jealous, and in anger, she transformed Callisto into a bear. She would have done the same or worse to her son, but Zeus hid Arcas in an area of Greece, which would come to be called Arcadia, in his honor. Arcas was given into a care of one of the Pleiades, Maia. There, Arcas safely lived until one day, during one of the court feasts held by king [Lycaon](#) (Arcas' maternal grandfather), Arcas was placed upon the burning altar as a sacrifice to the gods. He then said to Zeus, "If you think that you are so clever, make your son

detailed in this paper.

whole and un-harmed". Zeus became enraged and made Arcas whole and directed his anger toward Lycaon, turning him into the first werewolf.

Then, Arcas became the new king of Arcadia and the country's greatest hunter. One day, when Arcas went hunting in the woods, he came across his mother. Seeing her son after so long, she went forth to embrace him. Not knowing that the bear was his mother, he went to kill her with an arrow. In one version of the story, Arcas hunted Callisto because she had entered the forbidden sanctuary of Zeus on Mt. Lykaion. Zeus however, watching over them, stopped Arcas from shooting Callisto and raised them into the heavens as constellations (Boötes and Ursa Major). When Hera heard of that, she became so angry that she asked [Tethys](#) to keep them in a certain place so that the constellations would never sink below the horizon and receive water.

I think Arkas was associated with agriculture because the Great Bear constellation is also viewed as a plough-wagon pulled by oxen (not all ploughs were wagons, but in relation to the Big Dipper/Great Bear, it was pictured as a wagon). The bread association is more complex, involving not just the wagon pulled by oxen, but also round cakes used in Artemis rituals, connected with the round moon and probably also identified with the turning of the heavens; and the main Ancient Greek word for bread was *ἄρτος* (*artos*)="a cake or loaf of wheat bread": I have two theories about this *ἄρτος* word, a word which is of undetermined etymology: 1) the word may have been applied to bread because in earlier times an Artemis-goddess (or a son of the Artemis-goddess, like Arkas) was associated or identified with the Plough-Wagon pulled by oxen, and from there, and/or from round cakes being associated with Artemis, the word was coined from the Art- stem, to be applied to bread.

More likely perhaps is my second theory: 2) that *ἄρτος* derives from the earlier meaning "prepared" or "put together", in both cases from PIE *h₂er- "to fit; to join; to put together"; see Tocharian A *ārwar* meaning "prepared, ready; eager, willing" and Tocharian B *ārwer* meaning "prepared, ready; eager, willing", both from Proto-Tocharian **ārwer*, from PIE *h₂er-="to fit together; to join together"¹⁰, and see Old Norse *gerð* meaning "yeast, ferment", deriving from Proto-Germanic **garwijana* ("to prepare"), which however does not derive from PIE *h₂er-. See also Old Norse *gera* ("to prepare, make ready"), Old Dutch *gerwen* ("to prepare"), Old English *gierwan* ("to concoct").

Arkas is thought to mean "bear": while it is cognate with Arkos/Arktos meaning "bear", I expect that in earlier times, Arkas would have been understood as meaning "Hunter".

The tradition of Arkas having taught people "weaving and baking bread" curiously recalls not only the Ancient Greek word *ἄρτος* (*artos*), but also the Ancient Greek words *ἄρᾶχνη*

10 In the second draft from January 26th, 2024, interpret this word as being derived from the earlier meaning "a chunk, a morsel, a piece", as we see with Old Armenian *պատար* (*patař*) which means "piece, morsel (especially of bread)" and Old Armenian *պատարեմ* (*patařem*) "to tear to pieces", and with Middle High German *brocke*, which means "a broken-off piece, especially of bread, and there are probably more such examples in IE; outside of IE, I know of Proto-Algonquin **pahkwešikan* "bread", from *pahkweši* ("cut a piece off") plus the suffix *-ikani*, which is a type of suffix called a normalizer.

However, I no longer believe that there was an "art-" that meant "to cut" in IE, nor even in a hypothetical Non-IE Pre-Greek language that lent to Greek. In the second and first drafts, I interpreted *artamos* ("butcher, cook") and *artameō* ("to cut in pieces, to rend") as deriving from an "art-" that meant "to cut", but I prefer my new etymology where the verb derives from the noun *artamos*, and the noun derives from "the one who prepares", explaining "cook" as well as "butcher".

(arákhnē) /ἄραχνης/ἄραχνας /ἄραχνος, and Latin *arānea/arāneus*, all meaning “spider” as well as having additional meanings; and Arkas teaching weaving also recalls the Ancient Greek words ἄρκυς (“net”), ἀρκῆνη (“bar to which the threads of a loom are fastened, warp beam”); and ἄρκευθος (=“juniper; phoenician cedar; prickly cedar”), since junipers were used so much for weaving; ἄρκευθος is very similar in form and meaning to ἄργετος “a Cretan word for juniper”. For a discussion of the similarities mentioned in this paragraph, one can check Part 7 of this paper.

In part 3 of this paper I present what I think is the actual etymology of the Thracian Artemis-like goddess Kotys/Kottyto, and that theonym most likely derives from another root that meant “a strong vehement force; a violent force”, and if so, that would be great support for this new etymology of Artemis. I will discuss Kotys/Kottyto in Part 3 of this paper, because there is more that needs to be detailed to show the very likely existence of a root **h₂er*, “a strong vehement force; often a violent force”.

The next word that I will discuss as a great potential indication of my theory is Ancient Greek ἀρτεμισία=“wormwood”, a plant which usually (the English words “wormwood” and “mugwort” seem to be two of the exceptions) was named after its bitter taste: words for “bitter” usually derive from earlier meanings such as “sharp; pricking; stinging; pungent; stabbing; pointed” or from “burning” or from “strong”: in the case of ἀρτεμισία I think the word derives “pungent, stinging” from the earlier meaning “vehemently strong, violent”, from **h₂er*, “a strong vehement force; often a violent force”.

So I do not think that the plant was simply named after Artemis: there is a theory that the plant is named after Artemis because wormwood was used to induce childbirth, and childbirth was one of the things that pertained to Artemis; there probably was a second intended meaning referring to how the plant pushes/drives the baby to come out, and that would again derive from **h₂er*, “a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels; often a violent force”.

Artemis/Artamis/Artimus was thought of as a goddess that helps drive babies to come out, and so I expect that she was also associated with the germinating and sprouting of seeds, not just with the birth of humans and animals (animals were another thing associated with Artemis, as well as the woods/forests).

The Ancient Greek words ἀρίς (“bow-drill” and “a carpenter’s tool, an auger or drill”¹¹) was of unknown etymology and unknown origin: in the light of what I discussed above, it very likely derives from “that which drives the flame to arise, to burst forth” and/or “that which forcefully and violently goes into the wood”; the meaning “a carpenter’s tool, an auger or drill” could simply have been transferred from the “bow-drill” meaning, from the way a bow-drill drills into the wood; or the meaning “a carpenter’s tool, an auger or drill” could go back directly to “a vehement force that strikes against the wood”, as we see with Albanian “gdhend” meaning “to trim, smooth out, plane (wood)”, and “to carve, sculpture; to give form”, with the g- being from a prefix “gë”, and the *dhend* portion attested on its own in Old Albanian with one or more of those meanings (“to trim, smooth out, plane wood”, “to carve, sculpture; to give form”), and according to Orel deriving “from Proto-Albanian *denta, from PIE **den-* “to push, beat””¹². And the Albanian example wouldn’t be the only example of a word with such meanings and similar meanings deriving from “to push, beat, hit, strike”. I emphasize “to push”, since that best fits the root that I posit as the source of ἀρίς : PIE **h₂er*; “a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels; often a violent force”, like a bow-drill drilling into wood, or a carpenter’s auger or drill.

A bow-drill turning also reminds me of the turning of the Axis Mundi, the Axis Pole (whose northern end is the North Pole), the World Tree/the World Mountain.

Ariadne in Ancient Greek myth received the Crown of the Corona Borealis from Dionysus; the Corona Borealis is of course above the earth’s north pole, at the sky’s apparent north pole. Ariadne is of unknown etymology. Considering the similarity to the word ἀρίς discussed above, and the similarity of the idea of a bow-drill to the Axis Mundi, with the Corona Borealis atop the north pole of the Axis Mundi¹³---it does seem likely that the Ari- of Ariadne derives from “a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels”. The -adne/-dne portion may be only a suffix or it may be the second word of a two-word compound. Ariadne has been speculated to have been a major Pre-Greek Ceran goddess. The Romans identified Ariadne with Proserpina (Persephone).

11 The LSJ (1940) erroneously indicates that ἀρίς had an additional meaning “shrine”, but a look at the passage in Procopius’ *De Aedificiis* (Book 2, Chapter 3) shows that the meaning used in Procopius is “sluice-gate”, not “shrine”, as seen in the original Greek text and in English translations such as this one available here: [LacusCurtius • Procopius — The Buildings: Book 2 \(uchicago.edu\)](http://www.uchicago.edu/~lacuscurtius/Procopius---The%20Buildings:Book%20(u)chicago.edu)

“At a place about forty feet removed from the outer fortifications (**proteichisma**) of the city, between the two cliffs between which the river runs, he constructed a barrier (**antiteichisma**) of proper thickness and height. The ends of this he so mortised into each of the two cliffs, that the water of the river could not possibly get by that point, even if it should come down very violently. This structure is called by those skilled in such matters a dam (**phraktes**) or flood-gate (**aris**), or whatever else they please.”

If one searches online, they will find that that such many of the old style of sluice-gates (see for example this one: [An ancient \(Middle Ages\) sluice gate crossing a village stream in... | Download Scientific Diagram \(researchgate.net\)](http://www.researchgate.net)) look like a bow-drill. So sluice-gates were called ἀρίς because they looked like bow-drills, and therefore the meaning “sluice-gate” does not add anything to the etymology, and the word ἀρίς never referred to a shrine, as LSJ’s entry for ἀρίς erroneously states.

Ἀρίς referring to the plant “common dragon arum” (see the LSJ entry for ἀρίς) also comes simply from the plant looking like a bow-drill, the way the long pointed spadix is stuck in the flower like the drill part of a bow-drill.

12 Orel, Vladimir (1998), in *Albanian Etymological Dictionary*, Leiden, Boston, Köln: Brill, pg. 175

13 For the Corona Borealis atop the North Pole of the Axis Mundi, see for example this site: <http://ancientlights.org/CalendarHouse/ch6.html>

The similarity of Arkas (as a teacher of the art of weaving) with the name Ariadne (in her aspect of a weaving goddess, and who can forget Ariadne's ball of yarn in the Minotaur myth) is curious, and if Arkas is cognate to **h₂t^hko-* ("bear") in turn from **h₂er*, "a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels", then Arkas would ultimately be cognate (via **h₂er-*) to the Ari- of Ariadne, if that Ari- derives from the same **h₂er*; as I described above.

I will now discuss the etymology of Kotys/Kottyto and Bendis/Mendis in Part 3 of this paper.

Part 3: Kottyto/Kotys and Bendis/Mendis

I posit that Kotys/Kottyto (the name of another Thracian version of Artemis, though Ara Zea may be a Paionian or Illyrian version) derives from a *kot(t)-* in Thracian from a root originally meaning "a vehemently strong force that drives, impels, pushes; force; a power that is violent in its vehemence" (violent in the sense of, for example, the Big Bang or a supernova),

and from there developing additional meanings such as "swift, fast" and "wild" and "angry" and words having to do with violence, with battle, with fighting (Kotys/Kottyto was a huntress but also a warrior-like figure, more so than the usual Artemis goddesses, which usually weren't warrior goddesses).

This explains a Dacian word *cotiata* referring to quickgrass which grows very fast and energetically¹⁴. This explains also a Hesychius gloss where a word *kottos* in Ancient Greek means "horse", and this *kottos* meaning "horse" was another word of unknown etymology: I derive it from *kot(t)-* meaning "full of a strong force", referring both to the speed of the horse and to the sexual virility of male horses, a sexual virility which caused horses, like goats, to be very much associated with the devil in Christian Europe and elsewhere.

The Romanian word *ciot* (already considered to be a from Paleo-Balkan word, but of unknown etymology) meaning "stump of tree (part left over after it has been cut); knot on a tree, nubble on a tree; stub or small piece in general" I derive from "a hard compact mass" (originally not only small compact hard masses, but the meaning shifted towards small), in turn from "hard, firm, strong", from "a strong vehement force/entity".

Another Romanian word already considered to be a Paleo-Balkan word, and again of unknown etymology, is *cotor*, meaning: "stalk, stem, spine (of a book), apple core (the axis-like part of an apple left after eating the edible parts)": I derive these meanings from the earlier unattested Thracian *kot(t)-* "the axis of the earth", which would have referred to the Axis Mundi that is driven by a

14 The Romanian linguist Sorin Paliga was I think the first to posit that Dacian *cotiata* ("quickgrass") is cognate to Romanian *ciot* and to Thracian *Kotys/Kottyto*, but he did not connect them via the semantics that I do: he has a different theory for the root-meaning of *Kotys/Kottyto*: but my theory is the correct one. I credit him though for giving me the idea that *ciot* is cognate to Dacian *cotiata* and to Thracian *Kotys/Kottyto*. I also add the Romanian word *cotor*, which he may or may not have cited as an additional cognate as well: in any case, he did not posit the root-meanings that I posit.

vehemently strong force. The “apple core” meaning thus compares an apple to the earth, and the left-over apple core part to the axis mundi.

The “wild” semantic I posit is seen in Ancient Greek kotinos referring to wild olive trees: an Ancient Greek word of unknown etymology and unknown origin. I posit that the “wild” semantic came from “vehemently strong and often violent”, so no need for the “wild” meaning to derive from “pricked, goaded” as I proposed in January 2024 ¹⁵.

Similarly, another Ancient Greek word (Laconian Ancient Greek) for the wild olive tree also derives from the meaning “wild”, at least according to me: see ἄγριππος / ἄγριφος= “wild olive tree”, which I derive from Ancient Greek ἄγριος “wild”, with unclear suffixes.

Compare Ancient Greek κότος = “rancour, animosity”, and Ancient Greek κοτέω = “I am angry, incensed”, which could both be from “angry”, from “violent; a vehement force”. Compare PIE **kéh₃tus* “fight” and PIE **kéh₃-*, “to fight”, which could from the earlier meanings “a vehemently strong and violent force”.

And there is also a PIE **kéh₃-* “to sharpen, whet; sharp, pointed”, with a palatalized initial K sound: *k̑*. I suspect that PIE **kéh₃-* “to sharpen, whet; sharp, pointed” comes from “to hit, strike; apply the force to it so as to give it the vehement force”, and in 2022 or early 2023 I had written about how PIE **h₂ek̑* “sharp” likely comes from “vehemently strong”, which would explain the similarity to PIE **h₂eg*, “to drive” and PIE **h₂eks*, “axle, axis”.

If the meanings “to sharpen, whet; sharp, pointed” are from “to hit, strike; apply the force to it so as to give it the vehement force”, compare Albanian “gdhend” meaning “to trim, smooth out, plane (wood)”, and “to carve, sculpture; to give form”, with the g- being from a prefix “gë”, and the *dhend* portion attested on its own in Old Albanian with one or more of those meanings (“to trim, smooth out, plane wood”, “to carve, sculpture; to give form”), and according to Orel deriving “from Proto-Albanian **denta*, from PIE **dʰen-* “to push, beat”---I emphasize “to push”, since that best fits “a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels; often a violent force”.

The root of the Thracian kot(t)- discussed above should have begun with a non-palatalized K sound, because the palatalized K should have always been satemized in Thracian, at least/especially if occurring at the beginning of a word. So **kéh₃-* should be fine, but the full and original meaning was not “to fight”.

The Thracian *Βενδις* (Bendis; with a variant Mendis) was an Artemis-like goddess, and the theonym is of disputed etymology. Tomaschek in the 19th century preferred connecting the word with Proto-Indo-European **bʰendʰ-* (“to bind”), which might be compatible with hunting associations. First, the name can be interpreted simply as “Binder” and could refer to the goddess' ability to tame wild animals. Second, the meaning of **bʰendʰ-* might develop to the notion of “catching”: in this case, the name would mean “Catcher”, “Huntress”. A third, more speculative possibility would be to assume that in Thracian the development of **bʰendʰ-* has taken a similar turn as in Old English *bindan* (“to bind”),

15 I had quoted this sentence from a Sherlock Holmes story in support of that: ““In all our adventures I do not know that I have ever seen a more strange sight than this impassive and still dignified figure crouching frog-like upon the ground and goading to a wilder exhibition of passion the maddened hound, which ramped and raged in front of him...”. The quote can be found in Arthur Conan Doyle’s *The Case-Book of Sherlock Holmes*, 1927.

bendan (“to stretch a bow”) and that at the base of the name lies a noun “bow”: in this case Bendis would mean “Archer”.

Good ideas, and one of those may be correct. Or they may all be wrong. According to a linguist named Hawkins, no explanation proposed hitherto looks entirely plausible. He suggests to connect the theonym with PIE *wenh₁- (“to wish, love”), the same root of Latin *Venus*: this theory is interesting but not very convincing. Phonologically, the rendering of **u-* as *b-* in Thracian seems to be indeed possible, but this etymology does not comply with the main and most essential characteristic of the goddess, her association with hunting.

I once published in a draft that Mendis may be the earlier form, and that Mendis may be cognate with Proto-Germanic **mundō* and Proto-Italic **manus*, both meaning “hand”, from PIE **(s)meh₂* “to beckon, to signal”. The idea was that Bendis/Mendis meant “Catcher” from “hand”: but I know of no words from PIE **(s)meh₂* which developed the meaning “catcher, grasper” etc.; instead, for example, we see that from the meaning “hand”, Proto-Germanic **mundō* also developed the meanings “protection, security”. It is still possible that Bendis/Mendis meant “she who beckons, lures, enchants”, from PIE **(s)meh₂*, since in the Caucasus, there was a huntress, woods and mountain and dawn goddess named Dali who was believed to often lure/beckon/enchant men: but I have no confirmation that Bendis/Mendis was believed to do that.

I propose tentatively that Bendis/Mendis may derive from a proposed older meaning of *b^hend^h-: “a strong vehement force”; since I know that words meaning “to bind; to bond” (the meanings of PIE *b^hend^h- which can currently be verified) often derive from “firm, strong”: see Old Armenian պիւղ (pind) which means “firm, dense, tight, strong, fastened”, which Martirosyan derives from PIE **b^hend^h* “to bind, bond”. And see that meaning of ciot: “knot in a tree” in Romanian, and in Slavic and other language families we find words for “knot in a tree” and “to tie” (e.g. “to tie like a knot”) being closely and immediately cognate with one another (see Proto-Slavic **qzъ* “knot” and Proto-Slavic **vęzàti* “to tie”), and earlier I noted how “knot in a tree” could be from “a compact, firm, strong mass”, as is often the case.

Part 4

If one has read Part 1, 2 and 3 of this paper (without even adding in yet the store of facts that I will have in an upcoming edition, from various sources), then one has read about how likely it is that originally the Artemis-type goddesses were thought of as at least the female aspect of the force that drives the apparent rotation of the sky on the axis mundi (actually of course it is the earth that revolves on its axis and also orbits around the sun), not thought of just as Huntresses whose theonym derived from a root meaning “moving vehemently forward so as to rush in a chase after prey, and pushing the prey ahead” (as we see with some words meaning “hunter/huntress/hunting” and deriving from PIE **weyh₁*).

I posit that this explains some aspects of the Celtic goddess Artio seen in a Gallo-Roman sculpture of her: the tree in the Artio bronze sculpture discovered in Bern is the World Axis Tree; the Bear is the constellation Ursa Major (the bear was usually thought of as female in European culture). Artio bearing fruits refers to rebirth and immortality (fruits disappear from the tree, only to sprout from

the tree again next season), as does the pomegranate held by Hera and Cybele. Not just the fruits, but the tree itself is a symbol of rebirth and resurrection: hence the European tradition of the Christmas tree to celebrate and represent the birth of Jesus Christ, who rose from the dead and taught mankind about the soul that survives physical death. The Christmas tree, and Santa Claus coming from the North Pole; and the revolving of the heavens likened to the cycle of birth, life death and rebirth (albeit resurrection not reincarnation in traditional Christianity).

Considering especially the Artio sculpture found at Bern in Switzerland, it sure seems that the Artemis goddess was by some ancient cultures identified as a goddess of rebirth/reincarnation: this supports my theory that a goddess named Ara Zea or Arazea is being invoked in the Thracian or Illyrian Ezerovo ring inscription to facilitate rebirth in another life for the deceased and/or resurrection of the body of the deceased (this latter recalling Ancient Egyptian and Christian beliefs).

This also explains the bear pelt/hide/skin that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis the man was wrapped in at birth: the man who was said to have come back from the dead, the man who bore the name of a god named Salmoxis/Zalmoxis, a god who was likened to Cronus by many Ancient Greeks, though a passage in Herodotus' *Histories* makes Salmoxis/Zalmoxis and Gebeleizis/Gebeleixis seem like a thunder/lightning god as well: I think Salmoxis/Zalmoxis didn't correspond exactly to Cronus nor to Zeus, but was instead similar to both, as well as having aspects not found in either deities among the Greeks. A passage from the Rig Veda about Indra (which one can read on the next page of this paper) leads me to the conclusion that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis can be viewed as a kind of Zeus, as I have been saying more years, but I also knew that the Daco-Thracian Salmoxis/Zalmoxis (even considering the god, not just the man) was quite different from the Greek Zeus, and had qualities of Cronus, Asclepius, and taught knowledge about many things to people like the Libyan Atlas was said to have done, etc.

It may be that the man Salmoxis/Zalmoxis---whatever his mortal name was at first---after coming back from the dead and revealing mysteries about existence and the afterlife, was taken to be---or actually was---an incarnation of the Zeus-like/Cronus-like god Salmoxis/Zalmoxis.

The bear pelt/hide/skin wrapped around the baby Salmoxis/Zalmoxis combined with Salmoxis/Zalmoxis rising from the dead suggests what I described above about the Great Bear being the god of the revolving world-axis, and therefore quite logically associated also with the turning from life to death and back to life again, as suggested also by the fruits in the Artio sculpture, a sculpture which also depicts the world-tree of life and a bear.

Because of the Zeus connection indicated in Herodotus and because Salmoxis/Zalmoxis is shown wielding an ax in a well-known depiction from Thracian times, in other papers of mine, I suggested that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis meant "Chopper of the Oak" (with Salm/Zalm="chopper" and Oxis="oak", see that paper for details about that), since oak trees were known to be the trees most often struck by lightning and therefore oak trees were sacred to the thunder-god.

Then years later in another paper, I suggested instead "Lightning-Hurler" (with Salm/Zalm="lightning"; Oxis="hurler", see that paper for details about that).

I have since come to the conclusion that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis meant "Cutter of the Stone", inspired by Janda's etymology of Cronus (which I will discuss in the next paragraph), with Salm/Zalm

meaning “cutting” from a root **kelH-*, “to cut; to strike; to hit”¹⁶ (which I also posit as the source of Hittite *kalmisna/kalmisana*=”thunderbolt; log”, and Hittite *kalmus*=”shepherd’s crook”) and Oxis meaning “stone”, from PIE **h₂ók-s* - “sharp”, a root which is the source of Ancient Greek *ὄξυς* (=”sharp, pointed” and more meanings); **h₂ók-s* is in turn from PIE **h₂ék-*, a root which is known to be the source of a number of words meaning “stone”, such as PIE **h₂ékmō* “stone; heaven; the heavenly vault”, since the dome of the sky was often imagined to be a ceiling/roof made of stone, like the ceiling of a cave. See also Middle Persian *sng* (*sang*, “stone, rock”), Persian *سنگ* (“stone”), Parthian *سنگ* (*sng/asang* “stone”), Avestan *اسان* (*asan*, “stone”), *اسانگا* (*asanga*, “stone”), Old Persian (*a-θ-g* /*aθaⁿga^h*, “stone, rock”), Old Median **asan-* (“stone”) (>Old Persian *asan*, “stone”), Khotanese *saṃgga-*, “stone”), all ultimately from Proto-Indo-European **h₂ék-* (“sharp”), because of the cutting sharpness of stone.

In the name “Cutter of the Stone”, “stone” refers to the stone of the primordial sky, which was cleaved in two in order for the world to arise. See this quote:

“ Recently, Janda (2010) offers a genuinely Indo-European etymology of Cronus as meaning “the cutter”, from the root **(s)ker-* “to cut” (Greek *κείρω* (*keirō*), cf. English *shear*), motivated by Cronus’s characteristic act of “cutting the sky” (or the genitals of anthropomorphic Uranus). The Indo-Iranian reflex of the root is *kar-*, but Janda argues that the original meaning “to cut” in a cosmogonic sense is still preserved in some verses of the Rigveda pertaining to Indra’s heroic “cutting”, like that of Cronus resulting in creation:

RV 10.104.10 *ārdayad vṛtram akṛṇod ulokaṃ*
 he hit Vrtra fatally, cutting [> creating] a free path.
RV 6.47.4 *varṣmāṇaṃ divo akṛṇod*
 he cut [> created] the loftiness of the sky.

This may point to an older Indo-European mytheme reconstructed as **(s)kert wersmn diwos* “by means of a cut he created the loftiness of the sky”. The myth of Cronus castrating Uranus parallels the *Song of Kumarbi*, where Anu (the heavens) is castrated by Kumarbi. In the *Song of Ullikummi*, Teshub uses the “sickle with which heaven and earth had once been separated” to defeat the monster Ullikummi, establishing that the “castration” of the heavens by means of a sickle was part of a creation myth, in origin a cut creating an opening or gap between heaven (imagined as a dome of stone) and earth enabling the beginning of time and human history.”¹⁷

Here we see that it is quite appropriate to think of Salmoxis/Zalmoxis as a Daco-Thracian Zeus/Indra, as well as a type of Cronus.

The *salm-/zalm-* of Salmoxis/Zalmoxis I propose is cognate to Hittite *kalm-* found in *kalmisna/kalmisana*=”log, thunderbolt” and found also in Hittite *kalmus*=”shepherd’s crook”. From the root-meaning “to cut, to chop, to strike” developed “that which cuts/chops/strikes trees, etc.”, which led

16 The “H” seen in **kelH* means, “I think a laryngeal was there, but I have not yet determined if it was h1, h2, h3 or h4 (if there was an h4)”. For the **k-* shifting to z- in Thracian, see Thracian *zalmon* “hide, skin, pelt”, from PIE **kel-*, “to cover”; and that *zalmon* example also shows how the “el” of **kel-* became “al” in Thracian.

17 The quote is from the English language Wikipedia’s article on Cronus.

to “thunderbolt/lightningbolt”; and the meaning “log” developed from “that which has been cut, chopped, struck”, which is a semantic shift often encountered in human languages for words meaning “pole of wood, bar of wood, plank of wood, piece of wood”, including PIE **ǵ^hh₁ol-* (“pole of wood, bar of wood”) considered to be from PIE **ǵ^hel-* “to cut” despite the unpalatalized initial “g^h” of **ǵ^hel*. Thracian Salm-/Zalm- is most likely not from **ǵ^hel* – because initial **ǵ^h* most likely became “g” in Thracian, not “s/z”. While a PIE **ǵ^hel-* “to cut” is conceivable, I do not know if such a palatalized variant of **ǵ^hel* existed.

Gebeleizis/Gebeleixis---whom Herodotus said was another name for Salmoxis/Zalmoxis—I propose derives from Gebel =”Cutter” and Eizis/Eixis=”stone”, with Gebel=”Cutter” deriving from PIE **ǵemb^h-*, cognate with Lithuanian *žembiu* “to cut” and Albanian *dhemb*=”to smart, to ache”; compare also Ancient Greek *κῦβηλις* =”axe, cleaver, large knife with which cattle were slain”, of unknown etymology. Eizis/eixis meaning “stone” I derive from PIE **h₂ék/*h₂éks-* “sharp”, from PIE **h₂ék* “sharp”: the “ei” in Thracian was caused by the accented “é” vowel seen in **h₂ék/*h₂éks-*, a sound-shift (PIE *é > ei*) encountered often in Ancient Greek. Thus there is no need to derive eizis/eixis from PIE **h₂eyk*, “pointed”, but I will note here that such a root is indeed in the Indo-European handbooks.

The variation Oxis versus Eizis/Eixis across what were probably different Thracian idioms---or even in the same idiom, as the Greek examples that I am about to mention show---is no problem, since in Ancient Greek we find *ἀκίς*, *ἀκμή*, *ὄξυς*, *-ήκης* and additional variations of sound and sense, all from PIE **h₂ék* “sharp”.

For the suffix -is in Thracian nouns (the suffix -is is verified in Ancient Greek nouns and as a suffix for nouns in numerous IE languages, including Latin), see -zelmis in Thracian names such as Ebryzelmis: *zelmis* since decades ago has been quite surely correctly determined to mean “offspring, child” in Thracian, from PIE **ǵ^helh₃* “to flourish, to sprout; green, yellow, gold”.

And back in March or April of 2022 I first published my theory that the -tralis ending component of many Thracian names (occurring much more often than *zelmis*) meant “child, offspring”, from a semantic encountered in Tocharian B *akwam* which means “sprout” deriving from PIE **h₂ék-* “sharp” (see Latin *acus*, Ancient Greek *ἀκίς*, etc.), from the sharp point of a sprout piercing the ground as it comes up; this semantic shift is encountered in numerous languages, including in Romanian where one way to “to sprout” is to say “a *încolți*”, where *colț* means “corner, angle; sharp point of a corner, angle, etc.”. The semantic shift “sprout” to “offspring, child” is frequently occurring as well, for example in Ancient Greek where we find *ἔρνος* meaning “young shoot, sprout; scion, offspring”.

So I link Thracian -tralis to Ancient Greek *τραλλόν = πικρόν* =”pointed, sharp”, and as further proof I cite PIE **tréyes* “three”, which I derive from “middle finger”, since whether counting from the thumb or pink, the middle finger is the third finger, thus Three. And I derive the meaning “middle finger” from “middle”, which I derive from the earlier meaning “point” (I’m not sure whether **tréyes* meant only “middle<point” or whether we have **tré +yes*, or **tréy +es*, with the *yes/es* meaning “finger”: more likely, **tréyes* meant only “middle<point”), as we see with “centre/centre” deriving from Ancient Greek *κέντρον* meaning “center of a circle; point; something with a sharp point; a sharp point”.

My new etymology “Cutter of the stone” is better than “Chopper/cutter of the Oak” because Salmoxis was much more likely to be identified with Kronos/Cronus rather than with Zeus by contemporary Greeks and others; plus, phonologically, we find *Aigidava* in Dacian, with *Aigi-* by

consensus deriving from PIE *h₂eyǵ- “goat” a root identical in form to PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak”; elsewhere In Daco-Thracian we find Daco-Thracian onomastic/toponymic elements beginning with Aiz-, which again are considered to derive from a root with the form *h₂eyǵ- . So more likely, the Daco-Thracian result of *h₂eyǵ- would be Aig- and Aiz-, more likely than expecting an “s” after the “ǵ” in the Proto-Daco-Thracian oak word, which would result in ξ (-ǵs- becoming “ξ”). Ancient Greek αἴξ “goat” is from Proto-Greek *aíks; but -ǵs- becoming “ks” is not likely in Proto-Daco-Thracian, and seems to me impossible given what we know of their satemization; on the other hand, the shift ks > ξ I’m sure can be eventually proven for Thracian, including Dacian.

Plus I don’t know how likely it would be to expect the PIE vowels “ey” in that root to become “o” in a Thracian idiom, while becoming “ei” in a neighboring Thracian idiom. On its own, the shift “ey” to “ei” is no problem in Thracian, since in Ancient Greek “ey” sometimes became “ai” in Greek, as we see for example in the word αἴξ “goat”; other times “ey” became “ei” in Greek, such as we find with Ancient Greek εἶδος from PIE *weyd- , “to see”.

From studying ancient Greek mythology and other mythologies, I know that it was believed that the lightning god infused his celestial lightning into living things on earth, thus giving them souls and giving them life.

And Salmoxis/Zalmoxis the man (who was probably in relation to the God of that name as Jesus is to Yahweh, who was also identified usually with Cronus in Classical and Greco-Roman times, but sometimes identified with Zeus or with yet other Greek gods) was an example of how the lightning soul from Zeus does not die with the body, and man can survive physical death; and through divine power, a physically dead body can come back to life (maybe only if very recently dead). The “three years” that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis spent underground are probably the three shortest days of the year, when Salmoxis/Zalmoxis as the sun (identified with the sun as well as with the storm-god, as the prophet Elijah was identified with both the sun and the storm-god in European belief) “goes underground” then is resurrected: so then the man parallels the god thereby.

In pre-Christian European beliefs, I have come to the conclusion that not just the male storm-god (who was also originally directly associated with the sun, with the Great Bear constellation; with winter; with the north, the north pole, the Axis Mundi, the World Tree) but also the huntress-goddess was thought of as a deity of rebirth and resurrection. So I expect that the Artemis goddesses were often goddesses of rebirth and resurrection, not just of childbirth. A number of ancient ethnic groups in various times and places did not believe in reincarnation at the level of a shared cultural belief, while the belief in resurrection in the Christian sense never seems to have been particularly common among ancient peoples.

I will have more evidence in the next edition; in this edition I have described what I have described, including the fruits of Artio in the sculpture and the World Tree of the revolving sky, both of which are symbols of rebirth and immortality; and the revolving of the sky (actually the earth) was a symbol of a human soul going from one incarnation to the next as time goes on.

So my translation of the Thracian or Illyrian inscription on the gold ring found near Ezerovo is very likely correct (one can find and see my paper on that inscription if they wish to read my translation): the inscription is asking a goddess named Ara Zea or Arazea (both otherwise unattested so far, but compare “Deae Artioni” in the Latin inscription on the Gallo-Roman sculpture) to help provide

rebirth/resurrection. Zea is probably cognate to Zeus and to Latin Deus/Dea, from PIE *dyéws =”sky; heaven; sky-god”.

Ara is probably ultimately cognate but probably not directly (since the Ara of Ara Zea probably didn’t and never meant “bear”) cognate to Old Albanian Ar=”bear” (Albanian Ari=”bear”): Old Albanian Ar=”bear” is from Proto-Albanian *artsa, from PIE *h₂rtkós “bear”.

As with the theonym Artemis and the theonym Artio, it is unclear whether Ara derives from an adjective *h₂rtko- or simply from *h₂er- “a strong vehement force that drives, pushes, impels; often a violent force”.

As we will see in Part 5, we should expect Artak- for a Thracian form deriving from *h₂rtko. So if Ara is from Thracian and cognate to *h₂rtko, it seems then that Ara must not derive from *h₂rtko, but rather from *h₂er- , the source of *h₂rtko. It may be that Ara is from a language which cannot be regarded as actually Thracian; a language where, like in attested Old Albanian and Albanian, the “t” and “k” sounds vanished.

In Part 7, I will take a look at the possibility that Arazea is the form of the theonym, not Ara Zea, with Arazea meaning “Catcher”, referring to a huntress; from a root that meant “to grab, to grasp”, a root which may be Non-IE with Tyrrhenian cognates.

Part 5

In this Part 5, I will discuss some more lexical items related to the theonym *Artakēnē* , a theonym that I discussed in Part 1 of this paper. The main aim of this Part 5 is to show that *Artakēnē* is from the Thracian language. I don’t know why the palatalized *k of *h₂rtkó- was not satemized in Thracian, but there is probably a good explanation waiting to be found.

In Thrace, we find the river-names Artiskos, Artanes, and Artakos¹⁸: those Moesian/Thracian rivers (Artiskos, Artanes, Artakos) I posit are most likely from “flowing with a vehemently strong force”.

I’m not sure how the Moesian region Artakia derives its name: perhaps the region was named after a river (see the river-names Artakos, Artiskos above); or possibly instead after the Moesian-Thracian people/tribe called the Artakioi/Artakoi (a warlike mountain tribe, according to the Paulys Realencyclopädie). Their name likely derives from “vehemently strong; forceful; violent” or “the Rushers”.

18 See the Paulys Realencyclopädie der classischen Altertumswissenschaft, Band 2, 1 (1895) page 1303/1304. On those pages (actually two columns of one page) you will find the entry for Artakioi, the Moesian-Thracian tribe, and under that entry you will find mention of the region of Moesia (Moesia as in a region of Thrace, and adjoining Thrace) known as Artakia, and the river called Artakos. In the Artakioi entry you will also find mention of the inscription where the goddess *Hērā* is called *Artakēnē*, and there is also an entry for Artakene on that page where the inscription is again mentioned: and in that entry for Artakene the author states that *Artakēnē* was probably a reference to a Thracian goddess of the Artakia region and the Artakioi people.

In the city/town of Pulpudeva/Philippopolis/Kendreiseia in Thrace, the same city/town which was located close to where the Ezerovo golden ring was found, there was found an inscription in which the goddess *Hērā* has the Thracian epithet *Artakēnē* : as we have seen in Part 1, *Artakēnē* was most likely a Thracian Artemis, and *Artakēnē* probably meant “Huntress”, from a root “to push forward with vehement force, as a hunter chases after prey” as described in Part 1. The meanings “to push forward” and “to drive, push, impel” also suggest a force that can incite a seed to germinate, or a baby to come out of the womb.

In one of his mimes¹⁹ (“mimes” are short humorous dramatic scenes in verse) the Ancient Greek author Herodas/Herondas (probably of 3rd century BC Alexandria), an author of short plays called “mimes” (none of the extant mimes of Herodas have more than 3 characters) *Artakēnē* is mentioned twice as a daughter of Hecate.

In an Ancient Greek writing Hera is identified with Isis, while in an ancient Latin inscription from Apuleiua, Isis is identified with Juno (Hera) and Hecate. In the inscription from Pulpudeva/Kendreiseia, we saw *Artakēnē* as an epithet of Hera, and the inscription invokes Hera *Artakēnē* to help with childbirth (and to help the mother survive the childbirth as well as the baby). See this note for a source to verify what I’m saying, though the source offers no etymology and did not know what meanings *Artakēnē* conveyed beyond a being a goddess associated with Hecate and Hera and Isis, and associated with aiding a successful childbirth for baby and mother: ²⁰.

In the *Paulys Realencyclopädie der classischen Altertumswissenschaft*, Band 2, 1 (1895) page 1303/1304 it is stated that in *Artakia* is found as an epithet of Aphrodite in Mysia : Aphrodite was probably called *Artakia* in reference to “to arouse; to stimulate”, as seen with Proto-Germanic **artijanq* (“to provoke, stir up, stimulate, tease”) from **h₂erdi-* / **h₂erd-*, „sharp edge, sharp point, stinger”²¹. In Georgian mythology/pagan religious beliefs, a huntress goddess named Dali was a

19 In Mime VII (Mime 7), the one where the main character is a shoemaker and much of the play takes place in a shoe shop.

20 Radislav Hosek, *Hera Artakene*, 1963. Written in German, it is a very brief work of only 3 pages, but very valuable for helping me figure out the etymology of *Artakene* and the meanings involved.

21 By early 2022 (and maybe also in the latter part of 2021), I thought that the *Art-* of *Artemis/Artamis* likely derived from PIE **h₂erdi-* / **h₂erd-*, „sharp edge, sharp point, stinger“, the source of Ancient Greek ἄρδις=“the point of an arrow”, as well as the source of Proto-Germanic **artijanq* (“to provoke, stir up, stimulate, tease”) and numerous other IE words in other IE branches. So if from Pre-Greek, this particular Pre-Greek language (there may have been several Pre-Greek languages, some IE some Non-IE) could simply have been a branch of Indo-European where the voiced “D” sound in *h₂erdi-* / **h₂erd-* became the unvoiced “T” sound, as we see in Proto-Germanic **artijanq*. But I have found that my new theory is more likely: nor have I found (or I currently don’t remember) other instances where an Ancient Greek word/name of likely Pre-Greek origin shows a devoicing of PIE **d-/*-d-* to the T sound.

seductress goddess that had sex with humans, not a chaste virgin like Artemis. So this is likely what we see with Artakia as an epithet of Aphrodite.

There was also a natural fresh water-spring in Kyzikos in Northwestern Anatolia which was called Artakie, and in Homer's *Odyssey* Artakie is again the name of a fresh-water spring, this time a spring located in the land of the giant Laestrygonians²²: Artemis was closely associated with fresh-water springs, and I think it's likely Artakie as names of the water-springs referred to "a strong , vehement, violent force that pushes, impels> goaded>stirred up>flowing up".

On the same peninsula (formerly it was an island, later connecting to the mainland via a new strip of land) in Northwestern Anatolia where the city of Kyzikos was located, there was a city/town called Artake, and near that settlement there was a mountain called Artake.

The city of Artake (located where modern-day Erdek is now, in Turkey: the name Erdek is a continuation of the ancient Artake) could have been named after a water-spring, with the water-spring Artake/Artakie (or however exactly it was) deriving from "flowing up<stirred up/goaded<a strong , vehement, violent force that pushes, impels"? And the spring may have been located on the mountain, and the mountain was named after the spring?

Or the city/town could have been named after the mountain, and the mountain named after the Artak- named goddess, because "sightings" of the Huntress goddess may have occurred on and near that mountain, since the Georgian huntress goddess Dali was usually seen on mountains. And the water-spring named after the goddess.

I think these options outlined above are more likely than thinking the city was named after a goddess named Artake/Artakia, despite the example of the famous city named Ἀθῆναι (*Athēnai*)/Ἀθήνη and the famous goddess named Ἀθηνᾶ , Ἀθήνη, Ἀθήνα : but even in that case, it's not certain that the city was named after the goddess, or vice versa.

I have now detailed the lexical items which indicate quite strongly that *Artakēnē* is a Thracian theonym referring to an Artemis-like goddess. It seems likely enough to me that the theonym Artemis/Artamis comes from a form which was native to Proto-Greek, with close cognates in Thracian (*Artakēnē* and perhaps the *Ara* of *Ara Zea*) and in Celtic (Artio / Artiu), and probably in other IE languages, but such additional theonyms are not recorded in the currently extant material.

But it's also very likely that Artemis is neither native to Greek nor from Thracian, but from another IE language which was once spoken in the area: an Illyrian language (Illyrian may have been close to Thracian) or a Brygian/Phrygian/Mysian/Paionian language (themselves rather close to

22 The most accurate/scientific scholarship (see the summary of the situation in „A Commentary on Homer's *Odyssey*“, vol. 2, by A. Heubeck, S. West, J. B. Hainsworth and A. Hokstra, Clarendon Press, revised edition, 1990, pages 47–49) considers that the Artakie spring mentioned in the *Odyssey* is probably not the same Artakie spring that was located in Kyzikos. I also suspect that they are not the same; the Artakie spring in the *Odyssey* is more likely the Arethusa spring of Syracuse on the island of Ortygia. Likely „Artakie“ in Homeric times was known to be the name of a number of fresh-water springs among peoples who lived both east (east/northeast, e.g. in Mysia) and west of the Greeks (in Sicily), and probably also the word was used to the north and northeast, in Thrace. Thucydides and Polybius stated that the Laestrygonians were located in southeast Sicily, and in the *Oxyrhynchus papyri* (cf. *Oxyrhynchus papyri* 1358 fr.2), a work attributed to Hesiod (*Ehoiai*, fragment 40a) implies that the Laestrygonians inhabited the area of the island of Ortygia, which is where the city of Syracuse was founded, in southeast Sicily; and on the northeast coast of Sardinia, much further west of Greece, there was a branch of the Corsi people known as the Lestriconi. In Homeric times, it may have been known that Artakie derived from “goaded>stirred up>flowing”.

Thracian); or an Indo-European Pre-Greek language, which could have been similar to Thracian/Mysian/Brygian/Phrygian/Paionian or similar to Illyrian (and note that Thracian and Illyrian and Brygian/Mysian/Paionian could have all been spoken in parts of Greece before Greeks settled there, or could have been spoken in only some parts of Greece before the Greeks; and all these languages that I name in this parentheses are Indo-European), or an Indo-European Pre-Greek language which was quite distinct from and not particularly similar to Illyrian nor Thracian.

Part 6: Hera

Artakēnē was associated with Hēra and with Hecate and Isis.

For some years now (since 2021 or early 2022) I've been working on the etymology of Hēra (Ancient Greek: *Ἥρα (Hērā)/Ἥρη (Hērē)*²³), and I've found enough indications that lead me to propose, though tentatively, that Hera probably also derives from a root-word that meant “vehemently strong, pungent, stinging; a vehemently strong force that drives, pushes, impels”: many Ancient Greek words beginning with the H- sound are known to derive from ancient root-words that began with the S- sound. And I have found Ancient Greek words of unknown etymology which begin with Ser- and which have to do with “stinging” and/or “pungent”²⁴: they don't show the long E sound, but I have cataloged elsewhere Ancient Greek examples which show a short E/long E variation, see for example Ancient Greek ἔαρ (“springtime”) which was found in Attic and Ionic as ἦρ (“springtime”), and there are more examples of that.

σέρφος meaning “gnat”, little flying insects whose bites prick the skin;

σέρφον meaning “wormwood”, a very bitter tasting pungent herb which pricks/stings the sense of taste; additionally, as we saw with Artemisia, the wormwood was believed to prick and goad the process of childbirth, to facilitate childbirth, to drive the baby out of the womb.

σέρις/σέρεις meant “endive” and “chicory”, two more bitter tasting plants.

“Hera was the Olympian queen of the gods, and the goddess of marriage, women, the sky and the stars of heaven “---this quote is from Theoi's entry on Hera²⁴. So take note of “goddess of the sky, and the stars of heaven”. Since Hera was called “Cow-Eyed”, and since she wasn't associated with the bear, it seems that the culture from which Hera came saw the Great Bear constellation as instead a wagon pulled by oxen (as we find with the Septentrionis in Latin among the Romans), which would fit “Cow-eyed” as well as fitting a quote from *Suidas s.v. Kroisos* :

“Kleobis and Biton, Argives by birth, whose mother Theano or Kydippe was a priestess and intended to lead a procession in the traditional festival in a wagon as far as the temple of Hera; as the oxen were delayed, her sons bent their own necks and dragged the wagon and took their mother to the precinct.”

23 Ἥρη is the Ionic and Homeric Greek form.

24 [HERA - Greek Goddess of Marriage, Queen of the Gods \(Roman Juno\) \(theoi.com\)](https://theoi.com/hera)

In a temple of Hera Lacinia in Calabria, southern Italy, Hera was represented as a column made out of actual gold.

In a temple in ancient Argos in the Peloponnese, Hera was also represented as a pillar, which sounds like a representation of the axis mundi around which the stars revolve, and Hera (originally Sera?) was a goddess of the stars and of the sky, and like Artemis she was invoked for a successful childbirth.

Part 7

The tradition of Arkas having taught people “weaving and baking bread” curiously recalls not only the Ancient Greek word ἄρτος (artos), but also the Ancient Greek words ἄράχνη (arákhnē) / ἄράχνης/ἀράχνας / ἄραχος, and Latin *arānea/arāneus*, all meaning “spider” as well as having additional meanings; and Arkas teaching weaving also recalls the Ancient Greek words ἄρκυς (“net”), ἀρκάνη (“bar to which the threads of a loom are fastened, warp beam”); and ἄρκευθος (“juniper; phoenician cedar; prickly cedar”), since junipers were used so much for weaving; ἄρκευθος is very similar in form and meaning to ἄργετος “a Cretan word for juniper”.

ἄρκυς (“net”), ἀρκάνη (“bar to which the threads of a loom are fastened, warp beam”); and ἄρκευθος (“juniper; phoenician cedar; prickly cedar”) have been posited to be from a PIE **h₂erk^w-* “to bend”/**h₂erk^wos* “bow/arrow”, with Proto-Slavic **orkyta* (“willow”), Latin *arcus* (“arc, arch; bow”), Old English *earh*, source English “arrow”. Juniper and willows were also used to make bows for arrows due to their flexibility.

ἄρκυς, ἀρκάνη, ἄρκευθος and ἄργετος (via a Non-Greek IE language probably) I think all derive from PIE **h₂erk^w-* “to bend”/**h₂erk^wos* “bow/arrow”, and it’s unclear whether **h₂erk^w-* would itself derive from **h₂er* with a *k^w-* suffix; but it likely does derive from **h₂er*, since bending has to do with tying, binding, joining two or more things together; and bending can also to connect with the idea of a violent force, and with “to push, to drive, impel”>”pushing it, driving it, impeling it, so that it bends”, since when one bends a long twig, you are using your hand (or foot etc.) to drive part(s) of the twig in a certain manner/direction, so that the twig bends.

ἄράχνη (arákhnē) / ἄράχνης/ἀράχνας / ἄραχος, and Latin *arānea/arāneus* have all been proposed to derive from PIE **h₂er*, “to join together; to fit together”, in the sense of “the one who puts threads/webs together”, but I don’t know who proposed this. I have seen an etymology deriving ἄράχνη (arákhnē) / ἄράχνης/ἀράχνας / ἄραχος, and Latin *arānea/arāneus* from **h₂er-eh₂-k-sneh*, a combination of PIE **h₂er*, “to join together; to fit together” + PIE **(s)neh₁-* “to spin (thread), to sew”, with the *-νη*, *-νης*, *-νας*, *-νος*, *-nea*, *-neus* portion deriving from **(s)neh₁-*. I do not think that these spider words derive from **h₂er*, “to join together; to fit together”, and I’m sure that the ending portion does not derive from **(s)neh₁-*: instead, the ending portion is a suffix seen also in Ancient Greek ἄνδράχνη, ἄνδραχος, πάχνη (“hoarfrot, rime”) and in some other Ancient Greek words.

Nor do I think that these spider words come from “fast”, so they are not cognate to the Iranian-origin hydronym Arax/Aras. Nor did they mean “hunter”, referring to the predatory nature of spiders (but so many species of spiders don’t go out to hunt their prey, they lay on their webs and wait instead). Nor are these spider words from “round/to curve/bend” referring to the abdomens of spiders.

Instead, as I published in my July 2023 edition of my translation of the Thracian inscription on the gold ring found in what used to be Thrace, and as I have seen no one proposing before me in July 2023, I propose as I did July 2023 that ἄραχνη (arákhnē)/ ἄραχνης/ἀράχνας/ ἄραχος, and Latin *arānea/arāneus* are from “clinger”, referring to how spiders cling to various surfaces (ἄραχνης, besides meaning “spider”, also referred to a type of legume plant: which are viny, clinging plants).

In turn, from the evidence of the Arakhthos river and the mountain Arakynthos (both of which I will detail in upcoming paragraphs), the meaning “clinger” came from “to join together”, or from “to grasp, to grab” leading to “to join together”. If “to join together” in this case is older than “to grasp, to grab”, then these words and names may derive from PIE **h₂er* at a time when **h₂er* already developed the meaning “to join together”.

Yet Hesychius notes a word ἄρακος that meant “hawk/falcon”, and he says that this ἄρακος meaning “hawk, falcon” is a Tyrrhenian word (Tyrrhenian includes the Etruscans) word. And “arac” is believed by a number of Etruscanists to be an Etruscan word that meant „hawk, falcon“. Words for birds of prey very often come from the meanings of “snatcher”, “thief”, “grasper”, “grabber”, “taker”, “raptor”. I have considered a number of other options, and ἄρακος=“hawk, falcon” most likely comes from Arak=“to grasp, grab”, which in turn might be from “to join together”; but though the meaning “to join together” surely developed, as I will show with the mountain name Arakynthos and the river-name Arakhthos, there is currently no way to tell whether “to grasp, grab” came from “to join together” in this case, or instead “to join together” came from “to grasp, grab”. So it may be that “to grasp, grab” is the older meaning, and we are dealing with a Non-IE root.

This ἄρακος meaning “hawk/falcon” is identical in sonic-form and spelling to the ἄρακος word that meant *Lathyrus annuus*, a species of vetch: I have considered other possibilities as well as seen some suggestions from others, but most likely the vetch word ἄρακος referred to how the vines of the vetch cling, grasp and grab and twine around nearby objects and nearby things.

ἄρακος=*Lathyrus annuus*, a species of vetch; see also ἄραχος=the wild vetch, *Vicia sibthorpii*; and ἀράχιδνα=*Lathyrus amphicarpos*, another species of vetch; and ἄραξ (=arax/araks) is a synonym for *Lathyrus annuus*, mentioned above. And ἄραχνης, besides meaning “spider”, also referred to a type of legume plant.

These Ancient Greek words also indicate a root meaning “to grasp, to grab”, and this time developing the meaning “to hold”: ἀράη=“bowl”; ἀράκη=“bowl”; ἄρακις=“bowl, a pan”; ἀράκτης=“bowl; a pan”; and ἄροκλον=“bowl; a pan”.

Ancient Greek ῥάξ (genitive ῥάγος) and ῥώξ (genitive ῥωγός) meant “grape”, “berry”, “fingertips” (fingertips are grape-like in shape) and they most likely derive from a reference to the clinging, grasping vines of grapevines, later shifting to refer to the grapes themselves: a similar thing happened indeed with the word “grape” itself.

Now for Arakynthos and Arakhthos:

The Aetolian oronym (oronym=mountain-name) *Αράκυνθος* refers to a specific mountain in Aetolia which bears that name: *Αράκυνθος* is a mountain in Aetolia which is still known by that name today in modern Aetolia (in Ancient Greece, more than one mountain was called *Αράκυνθος*, at

least two: another one seems to have been in Attica: the exact location of the Arakynthos in Attica is as yet unknown).

One Greek website has this information: “*Arakinthos or Zygos, is a mountain of the Aetoloakarnania prefecture, south of Lake Trichonis and north of the Messolonghi Lagoon. It is 984 meters high. Arakinthos is located in the narrow gorge of Kleisoura through which the Messolonghi region is connected with the region of Agrinio. It is characterized by cedar forests, chestnut and oak trees, waterfalls, caves and a rich biodiversity of birds, reptiles, squirrels, turtles, deer, wild boars, foxes and wolves, composing a completely different landscape in such a small distance from the sea front of the municipality ICS Messolonghi.*”

Another Greek website describes the Arakynthos mountain like this: “*With an altitude of 984 meters above the lagoon of Messolonghi it is the natural border between the sea and the lake Trichonida.*”

Zygos (ζυγός in current Greek and Ancient Greek means „yoke“, with many additional meanings stemming from the concepts of „paired“, „joined“, „a cross-bar or strap joining two parts“, etc., additional meanings which are not relevant to this study) refers to the mountain being seen as the joining point of two different regions. See the quote: „Arakinthos is located in the narrow gorge of Kleisoura through which the Messolonghi region is connected with the region of Agrinio“. And see also the quote: „[Arakinthos] is the natural border between the sea and the lake Trichonida“. For another even clearer example of Zygos being used like this, see the Zygos mountain in Thessaly, which is named so because of a very important (very important to that region) mountain pass that joins two regions and allows for land travel through there without climbing any mountains.

So since 2023, I post that *Ἀράκυνθος* (Arakynthos) is from “to join together”.

And in this paper, I propose that the Arakh- of Ἀραχθός (Arakhthos) is also from “to join together”; see this quote:

“This dual spring of the Arachthos river, known since Antiquity, gave Arachthos its popular name, Dipotamos (Διπόταμος, "two-rivers"). The valley of the Metsovitikos river was the main passage between Epirus, on one hand, and [Macedonia](#) and Thessaly, on the other.”

And see this quote as well:

The Arachthos (Greek: Ἀραχθός) is a [river](#) in the eastern [Epirus](#) region of Greece. Its source is in the [Pindus](#) mountains, near the town [Metsovo](#) (Ioannina regional unit). The Arachthos is 110 km (68 mi) long and its drainage area is 2,209 km² (853 sq mi). Its upper course is known as *Metsovitikos*. From its confluence with the [Dipotamos](#) near the village of [Batza](#) it is called Arachthos. It flows towards the south, passing between the Athamanika the [Xerovouni](#) mountains. “

So I propose that the Arakh- in this Ἀραχθός (Arakhthos) hydronym refers to the two rivers that join at the confluence, and the θός portion I posit is cognate to Ancient Greek θέω , “to run, to flow; to fly”, from this θέω , “to run, to flow; to fly”, is known to derive the Ancient Greek name Θόᾱς. The PIE root of θέω , “to run, to flow; to fly”, is PIE *d^hew- “to run, to flow”

It might be that in the Thracian inscription on the gold ring, we are dealing with Arazea="The Grabber>Hunter", with Arazea from **Hereg^h / *Herek*="to grasp, to grab", rather than with Ara Zea="The Huntress Goddess" : if Ara Zea, then Ara (=Huntress?) is from **h₂er* or **h₂rtkó* and Zea (=Goddess) is from **dyéws*.

It might be that Arkas is not cognate with **h₂rtkós* , but instead derives from an Ark="to grasp, grab", which developed the meaning "hunter", and is cognate with the ἄρακος word which meant "hawk/falcon" and also meant "*Lathyrus annuus*, a species of vetch"; and cognate with ἀράη="bowl"; ἀράκη="bowl"; ἄρακις="bowl, a pan"; ἀράκτης="bowl; a pan"; and ἄροκλον="bowl; a pan".

Or it may be that Arkas meant "hunter", later also understood as meaning "bear".

* * * * *

3rd edition

A.G.

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